

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Start / Duration	1 January 2023 / 48 Months
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	15-04-2026	Version	2

Deliverable 4.4

Report on ML and DA developments for data-model integration in T4.2.1-T4.4.3

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Document History:

Release	Date	Reason for Change	Status	Distribution
0.0	07/01/2026	Initial document	Released	Internal
1.0	14/02/2026	Internal revised document	Released	Internal + reviewers
2	2/04/2026	Corrections of the submitted document	Released	European portal

To cite this document

Brajard, J., Cossarini, G., Bernigaud, A., Yumruktepe, V. Ç., Banerjee, D., Skakala, J., Tonelli, T., Puglia, M., Soto, C., Drago, L., Ayata, S.-D., Verezemskaya, P., Dechenne, A., Barth, A., & Greenberg, D. S. (2026). NECCTON Report on ML and DA developments for data-model integration in T4.2.1-T4.4.3 (D4.4) v2. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19593618>

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Changes from the first submitted version

- Correct typo in the name of the authors
- Expand acronyms (e.g. IBI, TRL, ...)
- Update reference list
- Clarify methodologies in 2.1, 2.2, 2.6, 2.7, 2.10
- Revise TRL in 2.8
- Improve readability of the figures

1. Executive Summary

Objective 6 of NECCTON is to provide Copernicus Marine with new capabilities for fusing numerical model simulations with both new and consolidated types of observations, using machine-learning (ML) techniques and advanced data-assimilation (DA) approaches.

These new capabilities have been developed in three main categories:

1. **Inferring new variables by combining observations and numerical models through machine learning (Task 4.2).**
This includes, for example, filling gaps in sparse observational datasets.
2. **Correcting errors or enhancing the performance of numerical models (Task 4.3).**
This covers model bias-correction methods and the improvement of physical and biogeochemical parametrisations.
3. **Advancing data-assimilation techniques (Task 4.4)** by incorporating new observations or improving the use of existing ones

Across these themes, a set of **12 algorithms** has been developed within Tasks T4.2, T4.3, and T4.4 of Work Package 4. The corresponding code was delivered in **Deliverable 4.3** (Cossarini et al., 2025). All algorithms follow the guidelines defined in **Deliverable 4.1** (Brajard et al., 2023). The guidelines and algorithms are available in the NECCTON GitHub organization:

<https://github.com/neccton-algo>.

This repository summarizes the key outcomes of WP4, complementing the already published **Deliverable 4.2** on PRISMA data. The achievements of Objective 6 are evaluated through three Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The numbers in brackets refer to the corresponding sections of this document.

- **KPI1-** “5 ML algorithms to produce 8 products”
A total of **7 algorithms** [2.1, 2.5, 2.7, 2.9, 2.10, 2.11, 2.12] improve existing biogeochemical products (e.g., chlorophyll-a), and **4 algorithms** [2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.6] enable new products.

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- **KPI2-** *“one metric per algorithm to validate the results and the progress compared with an identified baseline.”*
8 algorithms [2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 2.7, 2.9, 2.10, 2.11, 2.12] demonstrated improvements over a defined baseline. For the remaining algorithms, no clear baseline could be identified, and dedicated validation metrics were instead applied.
- **KPI3-** *“For 5 algorithms, estimate the efficiency to scale to realistic large dataset (>1 TB)”*
In **6 cases** [2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.9, 2.10], specific validation was carried out using large datasets. One algorithm [2.7] was evaluated within a full numerical model simulation. Details of the validation approaches are provided in the corresponding algorithm sections.

Additionally, **seven algorithms** [2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.9, 2.10] have achieved a Technical Readiness Level **TRL ≥ 5**.

Despite three deviations from the original plan—detailed in sections [2.6, 2.8, 2.9]—WP4 has successfully met all KPIs.

Section 2 of this document provides detailed descriptions of each algorithm.

2. Description of the ML and DA algorithms

In the following, a description and validation for each algorithm is provided.

For each algorithm, we include the link to access the code of the algorithm, followed by a **description of the algorithm** and the Copernicus Marine **or NECCTON product(s) impacted**, an illustration of the results and a validation of the algorithm on a **relevant dataset** using a **dedicated metrics**.

The algorithms are summarized below:

2.1 MuSt3Net in the Mediterranean Sea (task T4.2.1)

Emulator for unobserved variables in the Mediterranean Sea. A Neural Network allows to emulate the 3D results of a biogeochemical model also integrating observations from BGC-Argo data when variable is available (Task 4.2.1), thereby enabling a model–data fusion tool that combines numerical simulations with in situ measurements.. Potentially, the new algorithm can provide weekly analysis of chlorophyll for the Mediterranean Sea which is now part of the CMEMS-MED-NRT-006-014 product.

Code: <https://github.com/TeresaTonelli/MuSt3Net>

TRL: 5

Contacts: Teresa Tonelli, ttonelli@ogs.it

Algorithm description: A deep-learning approach to perform model-data fusion, focused on generating new 3D maps of chlorophyll-a by (a) modelling its relationship with physical variables and

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sparse chlorophyll-a profiles, and (b) merging in-situ observations (i.e. BGC-Argo). This novel approach consisting of a two-phase training procedure, designed to integrate different data sources, preserving and spreading their information. In the first phase, the network learns to model spatial and temporal dependencies using numerical model data alone, while the second phase then incorporates real float measurements, refining the predictions by adapting to in-situ observations and extending their information over the 3D domain.

Example of results: Chlorophyll reconstruction and integration in the Mediterranean Sea, maps (Fig. 2.1.1) and profiles (Fig. 2.1.2). Both maps and profiles results refer to test data.

Figure 2.1.1: The two-phase procedure and its application to reconstructing the weekly 3D chlorophyll field are illustrated. In the first phase (1st and 2nd column), we compare chlorophyll maps at various depth layers produced by MedBFM with those generated by our model, MuST3Net. In this first phase, MedBFM can be considered as a ground truth. In the second phase (3rd and 4th column), the reconstruction incorporates BGC-Argo float data (we consider only Delayed Mode (DM) and Adjusted Real-Time Mode (RT) data for the period January 1, 2019 to December 31, 2021). The 3rd column reports the ensemble-mean chlorophyll fields, computed as the mean of multiple chlorophyll reconstructions generated by repeated runs of the network of second phase, while the 4th column shows the corresponding ensemble standard deviations. To complement this with a quantitative evaluation, we compute the RMSE between the reconstructed profiles and BGC-Argo float data across different seasons and geographical regions, together with the corresponding standard deviations.

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Figure 2.1.2: Chlorophyll profiles for selected floats, including the corresponding WMO number and cycle to indicate location and time. Each plot displays the BGC-Argo float measurement (red), the MedBFM output (blue), the first-phase MuSt3Net prediction on BGC-Argo input (dashed green), and the final MuSt3Net prediction after the second phase (solid green). This comparison illustrates the prediction refinement after integrating the information from BGC-Argo data (included only in the second phase), evident in the improved alignment between the solid green line (final output) and the red line (BGC-Argo data), compared to the dashed green line (first-phase output) and to MedBFM output (blue line). This approach reproduces realistic values and profile shapes (e.g., correctly identifies the deep chlorophyll maximum) and successfully captures seasonal variability, learning to distinguish between summer and winter profiles.

Validation with dedicated metric on a relevant dataset – This study does not include a direct comparison with other data assimilation or data fusion methods. A meaningful comparison would require additional experiments conducted under strictly controlled and fully comparable conditions, such as implementing data assimilation algorithms using identical datasets. This remains an important direction for future developments. Nevertheless, to strengthen the robustness of our results, we evaluated model performance on the test dataset using multiple skill metrics, including MAE, bias and the Pearson correlation coefficient.

Table of skill metrics across different seasons

Error metrics (averaged over depths) between BGC-Argo float measurements and reconstructed values from the MuSt3Net second phase, computed on both train and test sets across different seasons.

Season	RMSE [mg m^{-3}]		MAE [mg m^{-3}]		BIAS [mg m^{-3}]		r		MAPE[%]	
	Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test
Winter	0.065 ± 0.012	0.095 ± 0.009	0.060	0.066	-0.023	-0.025	0.99	0.99	28.7	30.1
Spring	0.099 ± 0.015	0.124 ± 0.017	0.056	0.064	-0.016	-0.021	0.97	0.96	18.6	21.3
Summer	0.071 ± 0.010	0.078 ± 0.012	0.043	0.045	-0.002	-0.003	0.99	0.98	14.1	17.2
Fall	0.055 ± 0.008	0.049 ± 0.005	0.034	0.031	-0.001	0.001	0.99	0.99	20.7	18.4

Table of skill metrics across multiple regional seas

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Error metrics (averaged over depths) between BGC-Argo float measurements and reconstructed values from the MuSt3Net second phase, computed on both train and test sets across different geographic areas.

Geographic Area	RMSE [mg m^{-3}]		MAE [mg m^{-3}]		BIAS [mg m^{-3}]		r		MAPE [%]	
	Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test
NWM	0.086 ± 0.029	0.096 ± 0.032	0.049	0.059	-0.015	-0.024	0.98	0.97	14.1	16.8
SWM	0.098 ± 0.031	0.086 ± 0.034	0.059	0.050	-0.027	-0.019	0.99	0.99	26.9	24.2
TYR	0.094 ± 0.038	0.099 ± 0.042	0.063	0.063	-0.028	-0.025	0.97	0.94	41.3	42.1
ION	0.053 ± 0.020	0.055 ± 0.019	0.043	0.044	-0.003	-0.003	0.98	0.99	22.6	25.4
LEV	0.065 ± 0.018	0.066 ± 0.021	0.045	0.046	-0.006	-0.004	0.99	0.99	29.8	33.1

2.2 EmuPML in the North West Shelf (task T4.2.1)

A neural network deriving from a set of observable variables (surface phytoplankton functional type chlorophyll-a, sea surface temperature, sea surface salinity), atmospheric variables (wind speed, short-wave radiation), river discharge data and structural data (coordinates, bathymetry, day of the year), variety of surface and vertically averaged carbon pools: detrital carbon, DOC, zooplankton carbon, heterotrophic bacteria carbon and DIC. The idea is to apply this tool to observation data directly without the need to run computationally expensive marine model and DA. We envision that the algorithm could be potentially also used within variational DA (the current operational system for the NWES) by being integrated into its balancing scheme.

Code: https://github.com/neccton-algo/ML_carbon_pools/tree/main

TRL: 6

Contacts: Jozef Skakala, jos@pml.ac.uk

Algorithm description: Python code based on Keras/Tensorflow library, delivering a feed-forward NN model (in fact a deep ensemble of 15 such models was used) trained on a 5 year ERSEM model free simulation and validated using Copernicus reanalysis for the same period, i.e. the NWSHELF_MULTIYEAR_PHY_004_009 product. The publication on this algorithm is currently under journal review, but the preprint can be found in Skakala (2025).

Example: Example of results are reported in the maps of Fig. 4.2.1.

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Figure 2.2.1. 5-year 2016-2020 average concentrations for surface carbon pools, the first row is the free run used as NN training data, the second row is NN-predicted concentrations from the free run inputs, the third row is the Copernicus reanalysis and the fourth row are the NN-predicted concentrations using the Copernicus reanalysis as inputs (Copernicus reanalysis acts here as a test data-set). The bottom row is the uncertainty estimate, computed as a standard deviation from the ensemble, for the predictions in the fourth row. The Figure is taken from Skakala (2025).

Validation with dedicated metric on a relevant dataset – validated comparing the NN prediction from the reanalysis inputs (using reanalysis inputs for PFT chlorophyll, SST and salinity) with 2016-2020 reanalysis outputs (baseline) for the predicted variables. The metrics used were (i) biases evaluating differences between time-averaged values for each spatial location across the domain, (ii) bias-corrected Root-Mean Square Difference (RMSD) showing for each spatial location the RMSD between the predicted and the reanalysis variables, after bias (defined as in (i)) was subtracted from the predicted data. This should ideally impact future Copernicus products, e.g. by providing a computationally cheaper tool to estimate carbon pools than the reanalysis, or real time operational systems, or feed into balancing scheme of the current Copernicus operational system for the NWES (for some discussion see Skakala, 2025).

2.3 Interpolation of benthic traits with DINCAE (task T4.2.2)

Neural Network interpolation of sparse observation of benthic habitats using model outputs

Code: <https://github.com/neccton-algo/DINCAE-benthic-traits>

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TRL: 7

Contacts: Abel Dechenne, adechenne@uliege.be. Alexander Barth, a.barth@uliege.be

Algorithm description: DINCAE (Data-Interpolating Convolutional Auto-Encoder) is a Julia code based on Flux.jl library aiming to interpolate data points with a convolutional neural network (Barth et al. 2020, 2022). The training is based on 211 stations in the Black Sea continental shelf to which are associated to 27 different biological traits (Chevalier et al., 2025). Each trait has different modalities (3 to 6) that represents the different expression of the traits. To extend the training dataset, model outputs from the Black Sea (<https://doi.org/10.48670/mds-00354>) are used: average oxygen concentration, bottom flux, average Particulate Organic Carbon concentration and sedimentary flux. Along that, bathymetry and sediment types also feed the model. The output is: a map of the interpolated traits along the continental slope and an estimated error by the model based on the training data.

A baseline is set with DIVAnd interpolation (Data-Interpolating Variational Analysis in n dimensions, Barth et al., 2014) to compare the method to a regular interpolation. DIVAnd is an interpolation method that is based on a cost function and shaped by two main hyperparameters: Correlation length & observation error. The correlation length is a distance that control to which extent an observation will have an influence on the domain. The observation error is a metric that assess the accuracy of the observations. Both are tuned to lower at maximum the RMS error computed over isolated observations from 25% of the initial observations (cross validation).

Two main changes on the baseline & DINCAE model:

- 1) The methods are now used on the anomalies to better capture the average value of the traits as the observation's points are always close to it.
- 2) A mask is added based on the oxygen concentration. Any place where the average oxygen concentration is under 5µmol is not considered. Below 5µmol, oxygen conditions are near hypoxia and it is coherent to assume that benthic life cannot sustain. **Dataset size: 20gb:** Contains: [In situ measurements] Stations location & Traits proportions per stations. [Gebco dataset] bathymetry. [NEMO model outputs] oxygen content (mean & std), bottom flux, vertically integrated carbon content and average particulate organic carbon. [Sediment measurements] 11 sediment types are considered from EmodNet Geology.

Example of DINCAE model:

For this trait (1) and its first modality (T1.M1), expressing the percentage of benthic animals having a life span under one year, the RMS error is equal to 0.0903 with an RMS from the training dataset equal to 0.0788 (RMS computed on the training points) with a correlation of 70.3% with the ground truth. The RMS from the validation dataset and from the training dataset are on the same range which assess that the model does not overfit. The number of epochs is set to 1000, the learning rate is set to 0.00491 and decreases with the training.

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Figure 2.3.1. Interpolation of species with life span under 1 year. Left, base dataset without training points. Validation points are in the middle. Result is on the right.

Example and comparison with the DIVAnd baseline :

Figure 2.3.2 Baseline interpolation of species with a life span under one year.

The baseline is computed for the same trait (T1.M1; Life span under 1 year). The results show higher RMS compared to the analysis found figure 2.3.1 as it is equal to 0.1004. The parametrization is set to: correlation length = 80.000 ; epsilon2 = 1.

The improvement of DINCAE over DIVAnd is observed in most of the variables of benthic traits. It is suspected to be related to the smoothing performed by DIVAnd interpolation which reduce the variability of the field and then increase the gap with the validation points.

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Within DINCAE, the smoothness of the results is constrained by the Laplacian penalty which reduce the variability of the field. This parameter is then set to keep the variability over the field without overfitting, which is verified by the RMS of the training set, compared to the RMS of the cross validation.

The results will not affect other NECCTON or Copernicus products.

2.4 Interpolation of pollutant (Hg) with SOM (task T4.2.2)

Interpolator for non-observed variables using Self-Organizing Map (SOM) analysis on a dataset of mercury-related oceanographic observations. It loads the mercury (methylmercury –MeHg–, dissolved gaseous mercury –DGM–, Total mercury –HgT–), temperature, salinity, and oxygen measurements, normalizes them, converts them into a SOM-compatible structure, and trains a SOM using large number of training settings. After training, it computes the Best-Matching Units for each sample and evaluates the SOM’s performance using quantization and topographic errors. Finally, it saves all results to a .mat file for further analysis and visualization. This task has been conducted in synergy with WP8 for the preparation of a new dataset of pollutant variables.

Code: https://github.com/Marco-Puglia/Hg_SOM/tree/main

TRL: 4/5 Technology validated and demonstrated in relevant environment despite the limited dataset

Contacts: Marco Puglia, mpuglia@ogs.it

Algorithm description: The task started, in collaboration with WP8 activities, by preparing a new dataset of measurements of mercury, temperature, salinity, and oxygen. The algorithm consists of several sequential operations. First, data are rescaled so that no single variable dominates just because it has larger numerical values. This way, all four environmental factors contribute equally to the analysis. Once the data are prepared, the algorithm trains a Self-Organizing Map (SOM), which is a type of unsupervised learning method. SOM is a 2D grid that learns to represent the main patterns in the data. During training, similar environmental conditions are gradually grouped closer together on the map, while very different conditions end up farther apart. After training, each data point is assigned to the location on the map that best represents it. This makes it possible to evaluate how well the map captures the structure of the dataset and to visualize relationships between the different variables. The algorithm also examines how well neighbouring regions resemble each other. In the next step, the trained map is used as a reference to analyse new mercury augmented data produced using the output of the physical-biogeochemical model of the Mediterranean Sea as input of the SOM. These model values are scaled in the same way as the original observations to ensure consistency. The algorithm then places each model value onto the SOM map by finding where it best fits among the learned environmental patterns. Finally, the algorithm converts the mapped mercury values back to their original physical units and visualizes how mercury is distributed across the map. By repeating this visualization for different depth layers, it reveals how mercury concentrations vary at depth.

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Example of results: Fig. 2.4.1. shows the U-matrix (distance matrix) and variable components of the SOM form MeHg. Each map represents different regions of similarities in the Mediterranean Sea (black regions similar to other black regions and white regions similar to other white regions) according to the data. Fig. 2.4.2 shows the reconstruction of gap free maps of MeHg and DGM based on the trained SOM projections applied to the output of CMS model. The figure shows also the benchmark derived from a simulation of the BFM-Me mediterranean model.

Figure 2.4.1. matrix of the distance (U-matrix) and its sub-components.

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Figure 2.4.2. Projection of the SOM on the model outputs. Dotted are the values of the observations. First row: result from the WP8 initialization (MeHg). Second row and third row: results from the model outputs.

Validation with dedicated metric on a relevant dataset: A formal validation could not be performed due to the lack of any independent dataset. A qualitative comparison with the WP8 initialization derived from a model run-off simulation indicates that the agreement is only partially satisfactory (see Figure 2.4.2). As also highlighted in WP8 activities, although the proposed method showed promising potential, the very limited size of the training dataset has strongly constrained the quality of the final reconstructed 3D fields.

2.5 Nitrate bias correction using ML algorithm in NWS (task T4.2.3)

This work presents a new machine-learning reconstruction of surface nitrate for the North-West European Shelf, built directly from observations, riverine discharge, atmospheric, and Copernicus reanalysis inputs. The NN-derived nitrate field provides a consistent, gap-free view of 1998–2020 nitrate dynamics, and importantly, highlights the systematic biases that persist in the BGC reanalysis. Because the ML product is trained strictly on observations and well-constrained variables, it acts as an independent reference that can be used to bias-correct the reanalysis nitrate field across the entire domain. This allows us to map where the reanalysis drifts, quantify the magnitude of those errors seasonally and regionally, and provide a corrected nitrate baseline that is far more suitable for ecosystem assessments, eutrophication studies, and future assimilation into operational models. The dataset captures the broad seasonal and spatial structure of nitrate far more consistently than the existing reanalysis and allows us to identify nutrient-limited coastal regions, long-term trends, and how nitrate variability links to the dynamics of the spring bloom. The model’s performance is checked rigorously against independent data to ensure we evaluate the skill fairly. Finally, the product provides a practical and scientifically defensible approach to studying eutrophication risk and nitrate behaviour over a two-decade period, offering clear value for future model improvement and data assimilation.

Code: https://github.com/neccton-algo/NO3_Emulator_NECCTON

TRL: 5 It’s fully validated and first used in offline then on a subsequent work demonstrated in a relevant operational environment (e.g., bias-correcting real reanalysis fields)

Contacts: Deep Banerjee (dba@pml.ac.uk), Jozef Skakala (jos@pml.ac.uk)

Algorithm description: The codebase follows a modular workflow. It pulls together all required predictors SST, chlorophyll groups, NPP, river loads, ERA5 fields, bathymetry and time-of-year variables, aligns them on a common grid, and collocates them with ICES nitrate measurements. The neural network is built and tuned using AutoKeras, which handles the architecture search and training. Once the best model is selected, the script evaluates its performance on the independent test datasets and then runs it across the full 1998–2020 period to generate the gap-free nitrate fields.

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Example: input data from ICES (Fig. 2.5.1) and output of nitrate gap free maps (Fig. 2.5.2) for the North West Shelf domain.

Figure 2.5.1. The locations of the ICES data used in this study, split into training, validation, and test data. The data points are coloured with respect to the season in which the measurement was taken (a–c) and the depth range (in m) at which the measurement was taken (d–f).

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Figure 2.5.2. The left-hand panels show the NN-reconstructed 1998–2020 average surface nitrate concentrations for different seasons (corresponding to the dominant mode of temporal variability in nitrate). The right-hand panels show the same averages for the relative bias of the Copernicus surface nitrate reanalysis (Kay et al., 2016) with respect to the NN-reconstructed dataset (reanalysis minus NN-reconstructed dataset).

Validation with dedicated metric on a relevant dataset – The ML-based nitrate reconstruction was rigorously validated against independent ICES in situ observations over the North-West European Shelf (NWS) domain for the period 1998–2020. The validation dataset comprised >100,000 collocated surface nitrate measurements from ICES, spanning coastal, shelf and offshore environments across the NWS.

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Performance was evaluated using RMSE, bias, and correlation metrics on a fully independent test subset. Compared to the Copernicus BGC reanalysis baseline, the ML reconstruction reduced RMSE by ~30–40% regionally (depending on subdomain), substantially reduced seasonal bias, and improved spatial correlation of nitrate gradients, particularly in nutrient-limited coastal regions.

Full methodological details and validation statistics are reported in: Banerjee et al., 2025, Biogeosciences, <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-22-3769-2025>

This publication provides the complete metric breakdown, spatial skill maps, seasonal error analysis, and comparison against the Copernicus Marine biogeochemical reanalysis baseline.

2.6 Spatial distribution of zooplankton (task T4.3.1)

Machine learning for spatial distribution analysis of zooplankton diversity linking zooplankton taxonomic and functional diversity datasets (e.g. metabarcoding, metagenomics and imaging data from Zooscan) to physics and Low Trophic Level (LTL) outputs of the CMEMS GLO model. In particular, we used the GLO NECCTON outputs (1/12: Temperature, Salinity, MLD, Chlorophyll a, Zooplankton, Phytoplankton, Nutrients, Dissolved oxygen, Dissolved organic carbon). Indeed, CLS sent us the data on the CMEMS IBI config (1/36) in January 2026, and Laetitia Drago worked on it in January and February 2026, but unfortunately, she could not finish this part before the end of her contract.

Code: https://github.com/neccton-algo/PNMI_ML

TRL: 3

Contacts: Laetitia Drago laetitia.drago@locean.ipsl.fr and Sakina-Dorothee Ayata sakina-dorothee.ayata@locean.ipsl.fr

Algorithm description: Machine learning pipeline that aims to compute diversity metrics of plankton communities in the Iroise Marine Natural park and predict if they will be high or low based on their relationships with CMEMS oceanographic variables (temperature, salinity, nutrients, oxygen). After finding that predicting exact diversity values didn't work well, we switched to classifying communities as High or Low diversity using machine learning (XGBoost and Boosted Regression Trees).

Example of results: Size distribution of copepods in the marine protected area is reported in the confusion matrices of Fig. 2.6.1.

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Figure 2.6.1. Confusion matrices for copepod size classification across learn, validation, and test sets.

The model shows good performance with high true positive rates (High class correctly predicted: 39.8% learn, 23.2% valid, 45.0% test) and true negative rates (Low class correctly predicted: 42.8% learn, 43.5% valid, 38.3% test). Misclassification rates are relatively low and consistent across all three sets except for High predicted as Low in the validation set.

Figure 2.6.2. Boosted regression trees model performance metrics across learn, validation, and test sets. XGBoost model predicting copepod size (Low/High, threshold=0.92mm median) from CMEMS oceanographic variables. The main predictors for this variable were silica, mixed layer thickness and surface temperature. The model captured coastal-offshore gradients in copepod size distribution.

Validation with dedicated metric on a relevant dataset – To assess the algorithm's utility for the Iroise Marine Protected Area case study within NECCTON, we used a comprehensive dataset of plankton and in situ environment data (2010-2023, 16Mo) described in Drago et al. (2025, <https://essd.copernicus.org/articles/17/6583/2025/>) and publicly available at <https://www.seanoe.org/data/00943/105465/>. Plankton communities form the base of marine food webs and are critical indicators of ecosystem health, particularly in the Iroise MPA where fishing of commercially important species such as sardines depends on productive plankton populations. In relation with the stakeholders needs expressed in WP9, the aim was to test if CMEMS outputs could provide them reliable information on zooplankton community state. We developed binary

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classification models using XGBoost and Boosted Regression Trees to predict whether plankton communities would exhibit High or Low diversity based on CMEMS oceanographic variables. This classification approach enables MPA managers to better understand diversity shifts driven by environmental changes—a key requirement for adaptive ecosystem management and sustainable fisheries. Each variable was separated into learn, validation, and test sets, with performance assessed using accuracy, F1-score, precision, and recall. No baseline model was used as comparison. This work will be presented during the international OSM conference in Glasgow in February 2026 (Ayata, Drago et al., 2026). Unfortunately, we could not test the new NECCTON-produced CMEMS variables (from the Iberia-Biscay-Irish IBI configuration) due to the time of delivery of these products and the time of contract' end of the recruited post-doc.

Deviation from initial plans: unfortunately, we did not use metabarcoding and metagenomics data for this task, as we did not have the time to properly explore the metabarcoding data of the PNMI (our stakeholder).

2.7 Diel vertical migration (DVM) of mesozooplankton (task T4.3.2)

A Decision Tree approach was used to relate the underwater photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) located at the upper and lower boundaries of the high concentration layer of mesozooplankton (and small fish) to surface environmental condition (i.e. instantaneous surface PAR, daily averaged surface PAR, day-length, integrated food for mesozooplankton). The related environmental conditions and underwater PAR are subsequently coded in respective biogeochemical models for use during simulations.

Code: <https://github.com/neccton-algo/DVM>

TRL: 6 (the developed code has been implemented in NECCTON biogeochemical models and were successfully used in long-term hindcasts as project deliverables.)

Contacts: Veli Çağlar Yumruktepe (caglar.yumruktepe@nersc.no)

Algorithm description: The branch includes a Jupyter notebook and various input files that presents a generic recipe to estimate the upper and lower boundaries of sound scattering layer as a function of underwater PAR (photosynthetically active radiation) to represent diel vertical migration of organisms (mesozooplankton in this example) to be coded in respective biogeochemical models.

The notebook reads raw acoustics data (an example for a mooring site is included in the notebook), applies post-processing to prepare inputs for the decision tree training. The codes are written in a generic manner to replicate for any other region. The notebook prepares a dictionary file that has the inputs (i.e. instantaneous surface PAR, daily averaged surface PAR, day-length, integrated food for mesozooplankton) and underwater PAR located at the upper and lower band of the high concentration layer of mesozooplankton.

Following the creation of the inputs in the form of a dictionary file, the notebook applies a simple decision tree approach. For this case, as an initial approach and development towards a genetic use case for a biogeochemical model, the decision layers were kept minimal to be able to code the output

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in biogeochemical model fortran code in the form of if/else cases. The decision tree approach relates the estimated PAR to input data (i.e. instantaneous surface PAR, daily averaged surface PAR, day-length, integrated food for mesozooplankton). While the training data is limited to a mooring station in the Barents Sea, the output were used in multiple regional and global configurations for long-term hindcasts (WP5). The hindcast validations showed positive response from these different configurations. We note that the response of different biogeochemical models will vary, as such they may need tuning in various biogeochemical parameters. Since the training targeted PAR, it helps the genericness of the algorithm compared to if it was trained using latitude or topography as they are region specific. We further note that the training provided here is not definitive but showcases how the notebook can be used. With that in mind, new acoustics datasets can be easily used as an input to the notebook. We encourage extending the training data towards various regions to improve the genericness of the output.

Example: The use of the decision tree to obtain the underwater PAR values and use them to relocate a migratory organism (in this case modelled mesozooplankton) in the water column is depicted in Fig. 2.7.1. This is an example case tested at a mooring location at the Barents Sea. Fig. 2.7.1a depicts the observed high sound scattering layer (proxy to biomass) and Fig 2.7.1b depicts the simulated normalized concentration of the migratory organism. Given the limited number of input data (and its geographic limitations), the model captures the general seasonal patterns such as correctly locating the organisms near the surface during winter, and a continuous deeper layer in summer, and migrating to and back from surface to deep layers in transition months. The success of decision tree algorithm and its use in different locations should improve by including more acoustics data for the training. The parameters obtained from this exercise were coded and used in multiple 3D hindcasts in WP5.

Figure 2.7.1. Normalized acoustic backscatter density anomaly (a) is compared against normalized generic and conservative simulated migrating organism (b) at the ATWAIN mooring station in the Barents Sea (81.55N 30.83E ~800 m depth). Each box depicts an hourly day-night cycle averaged over a week. Shades of grey depict the normalized concentrations. Yellow markers denote the maximum concentration depth for each hour. Red and cyan markers denote normalized concentration = 0.8, depicting the upper and lower depth band high concentration boundaries. The weeks that are crossed out were omitted from the dataset for machine learning experiments as the defining the upper and lower boundaries for these weeks were challenging.

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Validation with dedicated metric on a relevant dataset

Figure 2.7.2. Simulated monthly mesozooplankton climatology (DVM activated: solid lines, DVM off: dashed lines) are compared to COPEPOD mesozooplankton dataset. The comparisons are divided into color-coded subregions as shown on the map where each point represent a COPEPOD data point. Comparisons depict average of surface to 200-meter range in the water column. Model climatology is achieved through taking averages of the daily model output of each corresponding month over 1990 – 2020 time-frame. The standard deviation of COPEPOD data is provided in shades of grey, and the number of sample points for each month is provided in bar-plots as shades of purple. COPEPOD data is available at: <https://www.st.nfms.noaa.gov/copepod>.

The outputs of T4.3.2 are parameter values that dictate the positioning of organisms that undergo diel vertical migration as a function of surface radiation. In this approach, we do not produce a large dataset, or a baseline as the reference to the produced parameters do not exist. However, these parameters have been incorporated a generic FABM coupler module which was activated for each biogeochemical model in NECCON and long-term hindcasts have been produced in WP5 allowing mesozooplankton to vertically migrate. As top predators of a lower trophic layer model food web, inclusion of diel vertical migration implies vital changes in energy flux in the models (e.g. mesozooplankton have less time to graze affecting phytoplankton growth, and mesozooplankton mortality is reduces which is a closure term). These changes affect from nutrient cycles to primary production and grazing. In this context, we provide mesozooplankton comparisons between without DVM (baseline) and with DVM activated long-term hindcast of ECOSMO model which T4.3.2 developed with against observed COPEPOD climatology. For every subregion, model mesozooplankton is significantly closer to the observations, mainly lower concentrations compared to the reference simulation, and are located within the standard deviation of the observed dataset indicating that inclusion of DVM in the model code has improved mesozooplankton biomass. The results of this work will be presented in OSM conference in Glasgow in February 2026 (Yumruktepe et al., 2026).

2.8 Fish migration (task T4.3.3)

A machine learning framework for simultaneous data assimilation and model tuning has been implemented in PyTorch. Currently, efforts are underway to apply this to horizontal fish migration, using an end-to-end differentiable framework for advection, diffusion and the horizontal migration.

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Horizontal advection and diffusion operators will be implemented for a staggered C-grid in PyTorch, and horizontal eddy diffusivity and ocean current fields will be replayed to provide forcing input. Additional horizontal movement relative to ocean currents will be computed based on a combination of physical (e.g. temperature & salinity), biogeochemical (e.g. predator and prey gradients) and spatiotemporal variables (location, time and incident solar radiation) and their spatial gradients. This movement parametrization, which will be implemented in PyTorch, will be based on an existing Fortran implementation already coupled to the HYCOM model. After developing the above framework and showing its parameters can be tuned in observing system simulation experiments, we will finally apply it to real abundance observations of fish, nutrients and other ecosystem components. The improvement in forecast accuracy resulting from parameter tuning in this fashion will be assessed.

This task is currently delayed relative to the original time plan, due to a necessary sick leave of the scientist carrying out the work at Hereon. Temporary replacements have been found at Hereon to carry on the work, which is expected to be complete by the end of the project. No other downstream tasks are delayed by the delayed completion of this task.

Code: <https://github.com/m-dml/coda>

TRL: 3

Contacts: David Greenberg david.greenberg@Hereon.de

Algorithm description: this software package implements CODA (Combined Optimization of Dynamics and Assimilation), an algorithm for tuning simulation parameters and sub-grid-scale parametrizations directly on observation data. During training, a neural network processes a space-time patch of partial observations, and generates an assimilated system state as output. This output is used as the initial conditions for a simulation, which is then compared to observations using one or more observation operators. By processing two overlapping windows of observations, CODA also computes an additional model consistency loss term based on weak-constraint 4DVar. Unlike DA methods based on supervised machine learning, CODA never requires access to ground truth system states. Within the NECCTON project, CODA is being used to develop and test parametrizations of horizontal fish migration.

Example: Several notebooks in the notebooks folder of the repository demonstrate how CODA can be used in several scenarios. These include data assimilation with a perfect model, data assimilation with an imperfect model, parameter tuning and learning of sub-grid-scale parametrizations. So far, demonstrations have been carried out using the simple L96 model, a 1D PDE with chaotic dynamics.

2.9 Super Resolution Data Assimilation (task T4.4.3)

A Neural Network allowing to go from a low resolution (LR) field to a high resolution (HR) field to do data assimilation in the HR space, to then go back in the LR dimension and only have to run a LR model. (Task 4.4.3)

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Code: https://github.com/neccton-algo/Neccton_Super_Resolution/

TRL: 5

Contacts: Antoine Bernigaud antoine.bernigaud@nersc.no

Algorithm description: This repository contains the Super Resolution Data Assimilation (SRDA) algorithm for the NECCTON project. It consists in a U-Net model, trained with weights that are downloaded in the notebook Test_ResUnet.ipynb, where the super-resolution can be run. It includes the code used for the training (“training” directory) and to run the full SRDA step (meaning upsampling of the LR fields, assembling of the super-resolved fields into binary files to be read by the model and downsampling back to the LR model) during the assimilation process (“SRDA” directory). The full SRDA algorithm requires an operational model and data assimilation codes and is dependent on them. Therefore, only the super-resolution step can be tried in this repo, and the codes in the training and SRDA directories would need to be adapted to be used in another setup.

Example: Test_ResUnet.ipynb can be run in Colab or EDITO (better to not have to download heavy files) to do the super-resolution of TOPAZ fields (physics and BioGeoChemistry) and get different metrics to compare against a bilinear interpolation.

Validation with dedicated metric on a relevant dataset – The Super-resolution step was validated on weekly data spanning 1 year (2018) and gave a consistent improvement of root mean square error (RMSE) of around 30% when compared to a bilinear interpolation baseline.

The full SRDA algorithm (super-resolution + assimilation of surface chlorophyll + forecast) was ran during a bloom period over 1 month (April 2019), alongside a LR run (starting with the same initial conditions), and both are being compared to a similar HR run seen as the “truth”. Each run uses a realistic forecast configuration with one hundred members and assimilates real observations (ESA Ocean Colour Climate Change Initiative data on CMEMS). The full testing dataset has therefore a size of approximately 845 GB.

The metrics used are the root mean square error against the HR run and the total time in CPU hours to produce an assimilated state (that includes forecast + assimilation for the LR and HR runs, and forecast + bilinear upsampling onto to HR grid + super-resolution + assimilation + downsampling back to the LR grid for the SRDA run).

CPU time is given in the following table in CPU hours for 1 member. The resources required by SRDA and LR are roughly the same compared to the ones required by the HR run. Note that this difference is multiplied by the number of members used (100 here).

	SRDA	HR	LR
forecast	23.5h	182h	23.5h
assimilation	11.9h	11.9 h	3.9 h

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Super-resolution (including downsample and upsample steps)	1.7h	0h	0h
Total	37.1h	193.9h	27.4h

After the first assimilation, for the surface chlorophyll, the RMSE between SRDA and HR is 31% less than the one between LR and HR, for every member and for the mean state (shown in Figure 2.8.1). The improvement holds for all the vertical layers (Figure 2.8.3).

Figure 2.9.1. Difference between the RMSE(LR,HR) and RMSE(SRDA,HR) after the 1st assimilation. Red colour means SRDA is closer to the HR state than LR (error in mg/m^3)

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Figure 2.9.2. Difference between the RMSE(LR,HR) and RMSE(SRDA,HR) after the 2nd assimilation.

This improvement however decreases to 21% after the second assimilation (one week later, Figure 2.9.2). This decrease is mostly due to the super-resolution wrong predictions over the Arctic, where it underestimates the Chlorophyll, as well as in the southeast of Greenland, and these errors grows over time with the forecast. It then goes to 9% for the 3rd assimilation, and finally -2% for the 4th assimilation.

Despite the great results achieved by SRDA after the 1st assimilation, the errors are amplified with time, making its prediction diverge more from the HR run than the LR forecast after some time. Further research could be done on reducing the super-resolution errors, for instance by adding predictors to achieves better result in the Arctic, or by restricting its application to the areas where it performs the best (near the cost or at the sea ice edge). Another solution would be to use the super-resolution to produce more accurate analyses but use the not super-resolved state as the initial condition for the next forecast.

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Figure 2.9.3. RMSE(LR,HR) and RMSE(SRDA,HR) after the 1st assimilation as a function of the vertical layer number.

Collaboration with ULiege

This task included collaborations to transfer the work done for the TOPAZ assimilation system to the Assimilation and Forecast system of ULiege. The pipeline would be the same: super-resolve Chlorophyll field, assimilate high-resolution observations, and do the forecast with the low-resolution model. The main differences being the domain (now the Black Sea), the forecast models (BAMHBI and NEMO instead of ECOSMO and HYCOM), and the difference in resolution between the HR and the LR field (factor 36 instead of 4).

This work then relied on the hypothesis that the algorithm developed for TOPAZ would adapt almost seamlessly to this new setup. This was unfortunately not the case: the large differences in resolutions for this new dataset together with the limitations of training data did not allow for an efficient training of the super-resolution Neural Network. Different strategies and techniques are required to tackle this challenging task, requiring more time and investigations and exceeding the scope of this project. For instance, a division in patches to artificially increase the training dataset could be a lead, but it comes with other difficulties, such as ensuring continuity between the predicted patches.

2.10 Assimilation of new type of observations (task T4.4.2)

Observational error covariance and model operators to assimilate reflectance measured by satellite

Code: <https://github.com/carlossoto362/diim>

TRL: 5

Contacts: Carlos Soto, csoto@ogs.it

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Algorithm description: GPU compatible python code, with a solution of the radiative transfer equation, (RTE) which computes the irradiance at different depths, as well as an estimation of the Remote Sensing Reflectance (RRS), as a function of the concentration of chlorophyll, detritus and colored dissolved organic matter (CDOM). The code also includes a Bayesian inversion of the RTE, which allows the estimation with uncertainty quantification of the concentration of chlorophyll, detritus and CDOM as a function of satellite RRS. From these outputs, an assimilation system can assimilate in an indirect way the satellite RRS, assimilation tested with the Ensemble and assimilation tool (EAT).

Example of results: results of the solution of the radiative transfer code (DIIM) are compared with in-situ observations in the North Western Mediterranean Sea (Fig. 2.10.1a,b). As a term of comparison, DIIM performance is compared with standard MedOC4 (Fig. 2.10.1c). Example of results for chlorophyll of the method applied to the PRISMA satellite data are compared with CMEMS satellite data (Fig. 2.10.2).

Figure 2.10.1. (A) Region in red marks the locations within situ measurements (x) of the density of sea surface chlorophyll, used for the comparison between (B) inverted values and (C) a standard ocean color retrieval approach used within the Copernicus Marine Service. The correlation values obtained for the inversion are comparable to current satellite estimations.

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Figure 2.10.2. Testing the

Bayesian inversion with some modifications to work with the data from the Hyperspectral Precursor of the Application Mission (PRISMA).

2.11 Assimilation of new type of observations in NWS (task T4.4.2)

Observational error covariance and model operators to assimilate reflectance measured by satellite

Code: <https://github.com/neccton-algo/Core-scripts-for-NEMOVAR-Rrs-DA>

TRL: 3

Contacts: Jozef Skakala, jos@pml.ac.uk

Algorithm description: Fortran code, modules for biogeochemistry balancing scheme within the NEMOVAR framework updating (deriving their DA increments) a wide range of optically active tracers from remote sensing reflectance increments. The method is based on 1D test ensemble DA runs based on which we fitted third order polynomial functions describing an inversion model deriving surface tracer concentrations from Rrs at 412nm and Rrs at 650nm wavelengths. This model was subsequently tested in 1D simulations run for the 2004-2017 period, assimilating daily Rrs observations across 6 wavebands (however, due to gaps in the observations the average assimilation cycle was around 4-5 days) and delivered 12-60% average improvements in Rrs forecasts (depending on the wavelength) relative to the free run, when compared to the satellite data. This is a clear sign that the scheme delivers an overall improvement to bio-optical tracers simulated by ERSEM.

Example of results: assimilation of reflectance was tested with the NEMO-ERSEM model in the NWS. Results, in terms of skill performance, of the assimilation run are compared with output of the free model (Fig. 2.11.1)

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Figure 2.11.1. Comparing the RMSE skill for surface remote sensing reflectance between the 1D free run (red), forecast (blue) and analysis (green). The forecast and analysis are from the run that assimilated satellite OC-CCI reflectance and used the balancing scheme (implemented in the 3D code) to update the ERSEM optically active tracers (including detritus, CDOM, SPM). All the model data are compared with the OC-CCI satellite observations assimilated into the model. The forecast corresponds to the lead time at the next assimilation step, which will fluctuate depending on the available observations, but on average is around 5 days. Whilst analysis just shows the direct improvement to the surface reflectance, the forecast entirely depends on the balancing improvements to the optically active tracers, as reflectance is not the model state variable. The different panels correspond to the 6 different assimilated wavelengths.

Validation with dedicated metric on a relevant dataset – the assimilated OC-CCI Rrs data-set was used for validation of the model forecast. The model forecast lead time was irregular, as it depended on when the next observation was available (the data have gaps due to clouds and/or low zenith angle), but on average the lead time was around 4-5 days.

2.12 Assimilation of new type of observations (task T4.4.2)

Observational error covariance and model operators to assimilate reflectance measured by satellite

Contact: Polina Verezemskaya, pverezemskaya@uliege.be

TRL: 4

Code: <https://github.com/neccton-algo/SORDA>

Algorithm description: SORDA – Spectral Ocean Reflectance Data Assimilation – is an Ensemble Kalman Filter based data assimilation system for multispectral satellite ocean reflectance, which allows for cyclic online assimilation or like in the demonstration kit, offline correction of BGC variables. SORDA uses Ocean Assimilation Kit (OAK) Ensemble Kalman Filter coded in Fortran. Pre- and post-processing is done with Python. Currently, six wavebands of RRS are assimilated into 7 BGC state variables: 3 Black Sea PFTs carbon concentrations, particulate organic carbon concentration, meso-

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and micro-zooplankton concentrations and gelatinous. Model used for system testing is a 3-D fully coupled NEMO+BAMHBI+RADTRANS setup over the Black Sea, permitting for explicit RRS assessment.

Example: Assimilation system tests showed significant decrease in MAE of phytoplankton and POC concentration concentrations varying from 25 to 50% (fig. 2.12.1). Diatom and particulate organic carbon concentrations are more affected by assimilation and are more sensible to assimilation cycle length. Emiliana and flagellate concentrations are less affected, due to the less wide initial spread of the forecasted variables.

Figure 2.12.1. Depth and domain averaged mean absolute error evolution during the PFTs blooming period (02.2016-06.2016) for (a) diatom carbon concentration, (b) flagellate carbon concentration, (c) Emiliana (coccolithophores) carbon concentration, and (d) particulate organic carbon concentration (all – in mmol/m^3).

In CDI and POC increment is evenly distributed over the depth, while for CEM and CFL the correction power decreases faster with depth together with the absolute value (fig. 2.11.2).

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Figure 2.12.2. profiles of mean absolute error for (a) diatom carbon concentration, (b) flagellate carbon concentration, (c) *Emiliana* (coccolithophores) carbon concentration, and (d) particulate organic carbon concentration (all – in mmol/m^3).

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